

DESIGN AND VALIDATION OF THE PRIMARY STRUCTURE AND BONDED JOINTS FOR THE NEXT GENERATION LARGE CANADARM TEST BED

P.P. Krimbalis^{1*}, D. Djokic^{2*}, G. Hay¹, R. Cole²

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, MDA Space Missions, Brampton, Canada

² Aerospace, National Research Council Canada, Ottawa, Canada,

* Corresponding author (peter.krimbalis@mdacorporation.com, drazen.djokic@nrc-cnrc.gc.ca)

Keywords: *Composites, aerospace, robotics, secondary bonding, bonded joint, design, large adherends*

1 Introduction

Following on the heritage and successes of *Canadarm I* and *Canadarm II* (also known as Shuttle and Space Station Remote Manipulator Systems, SRMS and SSRMS), the Canadian Space Agency initiated the Next Generation Canadarm (NGC) program to develop the “path-to-flight” technologies and prototypes necessary for the robotic refueling of prepared and unprepared satellites in Earth orbit.

One of five test-beds developed for the NGC program, the Next Generation Large Canadarm (NGLC) ground test-bed model serves to demonstrate the feasibility of a large class manipulator with a 15 m reach, comparable to SSRMS, that can be launched within the limited storage volume of future exploration vehicles by means of a 3:1 packing ratio. This packing ratio is primarily achieved by means of telescoping booms.

The work presented herein focuses on the design, analysis and validation of the primary structural elements and bonded joints of the telescoping booms employed in the NGLC ground test bed.

2 NGLC Design Overview

The NGLC ground test bed demonstrates a volumetric reduction in the launch package of a large manipulator system while maintaining reach capability through telescopic deployment and retraction of nested cylindrical elements. As shown in Fig. 1, NGLC is comprised of two telescoping booms, connected by three pitch joints. The booms consist of an inner and outer segment with a lock mechanism for both positions, and a rail network to guide their relative translation. This design configuration is especially attractive, as it allows for self-deployment. The pitch joints provide the actuation, extending and collapsing the telescoping booms.

NGLC bending and torsional stiffness requirements were met through the use of high stiffness carbon composite materials and structural bonding [1]. Both inner and outer segments feature a centre composite section bonded to aluminum end sections using a stepped-lap joint. The metallic sections of the inner and outer segments house the lock mechanisms, linear translation mechanisms, cabling, and provide the interface flange for connection to the rotary pitch joints of the manipulator. In turn, application of centre composite sections maximized global specific stiffness and minimized mass of the overall system. Also, the rail network was bonded to the Inner Mould Line (IML) surface of the outer segment. The use of structural bonding eliminated mechanical fasteners and maximized NGLC stiffness through a reduction of the clearance required between the telescoping assemblies and an increase of the inner segment diameter.

Each telescoping boom consists of:

- an inner and outer segment,
- a boom lock mechanism to structurally connect the inner and outer segment together in either the retracted or extended positions,
- a translation mechanism, allowing the segments to translate with respect to each other, and
- an internal cable handling mechanism

The rotary pitch joints consist of an off-the-shelf commercial motor/planetary drive unit, packaged within a custom housing to interface with the telescoping booms and the Mechanical Ground Support Equipment (MGSE) flat-floor rig.

3 Motivation for a Bonded Boom Design

The primary reasons for pursuing an entirely adhesively bonded boom design for the NGLC program was twofold: The first was to gain advancement in state of the art technology in the bonding of large, primary load path aerospace structures that can be applied to scalable designs that is portable to future applications. The second was to

achieve a fastener-free interface between the metallic and composite adherends, maximizing the internal boom volume available for the three mechanisms required for the telescoping aspect of the boom design.

A fastener-free structural interface between metallic and composite adherends has many general design advantages. As a telescoping boom design can be up to four times the mass of a standard non-telescoping boom of equivalent length and load capacity, any mass reduction that can be accomplished through the elimination of mechanical fasteners is beneficial. A continuous geometry, lacking holes for mechanical fasteners, minimizes fatigue crack initiation in metallic parts and transfers the load between adherends more efficiently, eliminating the load peaks that would otherwise be present in the legacy fastening design. For these reasons, an entirely bonded interface between adherends benefits from a higher strength-to-weight ratio over the legacy fastening design. Also, the bonding design presented herein is applicable to a wide variety of geometries and is not limited to circular cross sections or tubular structures.

In order for the NGLC test bed to demonstrate the concept of a high-packing-ratio telescoping manipulator of the size of the SSRMS, the allowable outer boom diameter was limited to 36 cm. The diameter of the inner boom, therefore, was limited by the diameter of the outer boom less the required clearance for the telescoping translation and lockout mechanisms. Maximizing the diameter of the inner boom was critical to the overall strength and stiffness requirements of the telescoping boom assembly. Clearly, if the inner boom diameter was sacrificed in favour of ample clearance for the mechanical hardware between the inner and outer booms – in addition to the historically used Hi-Lok® fasteners for securing the metallic end fittings to the composite tubes – the resulting inner boom diameter would have led to a boom design of underperforming stiffness. Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 illustrate the legacy method of using Hi-Lok® fasteners in conjunction with a bonded interface for securing the metallic end-fittings to a composite section that was desired to be avoided in the overall NGLC design.

Additionally, each of the inner and outer segments are covered with Multi-Layer Insulation (MLI)

thermal blankets, consisting of delicate alternating layers of goldized Kapton® film and Nomex® scrim cloth, with a final outer layer of Beta cloth (Telfon®-coated glass cloth). MLI blankets typically have an uncompressed thickness of 6 to 7 mm. During boom extension or retraction, the risk of an outer boom Hi-Lok® fastener snagging the thermal blanket of the inner segment as it moved past was deemed unacceptably high. If the boom were to bind mid-travel, the manipulator would be rendered unusable as NGLC is designed to react the full 1500 N-m limit loads only when the telescoping boom is locked in either the fully retracted or extended positions. At best, a tear in the MLI could lead to a host of complications including localized heating and warping due to solar radiation and atomic oxygen attack of organic resins, among others.

With this bonded boom design, the historical Hi-Lok® fasteners were eliminated, allowing the inner boom diameter to be maximized to 28 cm and a radial clearance between the inner and outer booms of 29 mm to accommodate the translation and lockout mechanisms, as well as the inner boom MLI blanket.

4 Design Requirements

Loads: To match the capabilities of the SSRMS, the Shoulder Pitch (SP) and Wrist Pitch (WP) joints of the NGLC are capable of a minimum continuous output torque of 1500 N-m. As such, the booms were designed and manufactured to sustain the following limit loads with the appropriate factors of safety applied [1] [6]:

- A bending moment of 1500 N-m applied at the end flanges about any axis perpendicular to the longitudinal axis of the boom,
- A torsional moment of 1500 N-m about the longitudinal axis of the boom, and
- The above bending and torsional moments combined.

Stiffness: Again, equivalent to the SSRMS capabilities, the stiffness of the booms was designed to be as follows [1] [6]:

- Minimum bending stiffness in any direction:
 $EI \geq 5.17 \times 10^7 \text{ N-mm}^2$
- Minimum torsional stiffness:
 $GJ \geq 2.57 \times 10^7 \text{ N-mm}^2$

5 Design of Adherends and Bonded Joint

In order to satisfy the stiffness and limit-load requirements for composite adherends, a customized lay-up was designed, using T800 carbon fibre (intermediate modulus – high strength), impregnated with a proprietary epoxy resin.

Several manufacturing techniques were considered for this application, including traditional hand lay-up, filament winding and Automated Fibre Placement (AFP). Given the complexity of the lay-up and the cost/schedule constraints of the program, a filament winding approach employing true axial fibre placement was ultimately chosen.

The lay-up itself featured a combination of 0° , $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° fibre orientations to achieve the target global stiffness, given the volumetric constraints. Considerations of symmetry and balance of the lay-up with respect to its own thickness versus a lay-up that is balanced and symmetric about the neutral axis of the cross section was central to the design process in order to maximize section stiffness. It is impossible to design a laminate with a changing cross section and a ply drop-off scheme that is balanced and symmetric about its thickness. However, a balanced and symmetric scheme is precisely what was desired to maximize section stiffness in the load bearing section outside of the stepped-lap joint. Therefore, a balanced and symmetric layup was used in the main section while an unbalanced and asymmetric lay-up was used in the stepped-lap section. The consequences of an unbalanced and asymmetric lay-up here is minimized by the closed section geometry.

The final design included a total of 44 plies, the final 15 of which gently built up each end section in order to accommodate the stepped-lap joint. An additional four 90° sacrificial plies marked with a tracer thread were introduced to account for thickness variations inherent to the filament winding process [8]. These were removed during the subsequent machining process.

The lay-up of the composite portion of the stepped-lap joint required much additional design detail since the final adherend geometry would be the result of a subsequent machining operation with tight tolerances. Considerations of tow bandwidth, tow cross sectional geometry, consolidation tension

vs tow angle, and resin viscosity/squeeze-out were all critical for the correct placement of 0° degree tows, whose location at the face of each step was key to optimal joint performance. Fig. 4 depicts the final geometry of the machined stepped-lap joint with the exposed 0° tows visible at the faces of the steps.

Similarly, each metallic adherend was machined as a tubular section from a single block of 6061-T651 aluminum, equipped with necessary attachment points for the internal hardware and pitch joints. It was well understood that the adherend materials are mismatched, both in terms of their Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE) and galvanic compatibilities; however, considering the test requirements (ground test) and cost implications, this was deemed acceptable.

Stepped-lap joints, matching to the composite adherends were machined after anodizing, thus exposing pristine metal. The fitted adherends provided an optimum 0.38 mm bondline gap.

To ensure the structural integrity of the design, detailed progressive damage Finite Element (FE) models of the entire manipulator assembly for the combined axial, bending and torsional load cases were investigated. Notable aspects of the FE analyses included mesoscopic scale modeling with ply-drop offs, a quadratic Tsai-Wu failure criterion and a ply delamination criterion.

Model pre- and post- processing was performed on NX 7.1, while the analysis was executed using 64-bit NX NASTRAN 7.5. The model itself was populated with a combination of continuum solid, shell and beam/rigid elements. CQUAD8 elements invoking the PCOMP material card populated the composite sections and a combination of CHEXA8 and CTETRA10 elements populated the remaining three dimensional structure. Fasteners at secondary interfaces were modeled using CBAR and RBE2 spider element arrays and static interfaces were either glued or modeled for potential contact with a double sided master/slave algorithm. External loads were applied at the face of the SP joint interface via an RBE2 spider element array acting upon the fastener hole pattern. A similar RBE2 spider element array was modeled at the Elbow Pitch (EP) interface to enable enforcement of a full 6 degree of freedom boundary condition [9].

All standard modeling checks were performed including free-free dynamics, constrained modes, unit gravity in all three global coordinate axes, as well as pre-processor checks such as element distortion, plate element normal orientation and internal angles.

6 NGLC Structural Joint Design, Bonding Strategy and Execution

A stepped-lap joint was selected for NGLC as this configuration provides the highest strength for assemblies featuring at least one composite adherend [2]. Preliminary analyses were performed using various numbers of steps within the lap joint. From these, a configuration with three steps was selected and analyzed in more detail. A step length of 19 mm was selected for high strength and the desire to keep the overall overlap length close to 50.8 mm. The inner segment bonded joint was selected for all analyses because it presents the worst stress case, with the same loads as the outer segment but handled by a smaller diameter article and therefore a smaller bond area. The rail network bonding was not considered critical, as these bondlines experience negligible stresses.

The bonded joint was analyzed using a continuum mechanics methodology featuring adhesive nonlinear behaviour employing an elastic/perfectly plastic assumption (*A4EI* program) [3]. The worst case ultimate load scenario involved combined bending and torque loads. For this case, the adhesive shear and adherend axial stresses due to the bending load were calculated separately from the adhesive shear and adherend in-plane shear stresses due to the torque load. The combined loading effect on the bondline, was determined using the Von Mises criteria method [4] (*i.e.* root sum of squares).

The selection of Hysol[®] EA9394-NA paste adhesive for all bonding operations was driven by the joint analyses, adherend material choices, their configuration and their geometry. Bondline thickness was controlled by limiting adherend translation via a combination of the bonding apparatus features and embedded steel wires.

The NGLC assembly featured two distinct adherend configurations, with respect to orientation and translation of their bondlines: perpendicular full-length bonding of steel rails to the IML surface

of the outer composite sections, and parallel stepped-lap joining of tubular aluminum and composite sections. Two different bonding techniques were utilized: simultaneous translation and bonding of the multiple steel rail segments to a single composite adherend, and sequential bonding of the various composite-to-aluminum segments.

A modular bonding apparatus was designed to accommodate specific bonding operations [5]. A flat, horizontal and stiff table interfaced to a stiff vertical post formed the basis for each apparatus configuration, shown in Fig. 5. The post was actuated vertically by a manually-operated geared mechanism which in turn actuated wedge mechanisms that moved the rail supports radially. In this approach, the rails were magnetically attached to the supports and the wedge mechanisms were retracted. The adhesive was manually applied to the rails, and the composite adherend was lowered into the position. The bonding surfaces were translated perpendicularly into their bonding position, expelling the excess adhesive to the sides and away from the critical rail surfaces. Fig. 6 shows the bonded rail network during the de-moulding phase, where the wedge mechanisms were simply retracted.

In contrast to the rail-bonding, a parallel translation approach of the bonding surfaces was used for the stepped-lap joints. This non-conventional configuration is generally more difficult to execute, but it has significant advantages in maintaining the tubular sections intact.

The bonding apparatus was reconfigured by replacing the wedge mechanisms with a machined locator disc, shown in Fig. 7. The aluminum section (stationary) was located and affixed to the bonding table and the composite section (translating) was affixed to the centre post via the locator disc. Nylon ball transfers constrained the radial position of the adherends while allowing axial movement. Relative translation of the centre post with respect to the bonding table facilitated controlled translation of the adherends as illustrated. The adhesive application played a crucial role in avoiding bondline voids. It was applied obliquely across the steps to both adherends as shown in Fig. 8, Fig. 9 and Fig. 10. Any air, trapped between the parallel adhesive surfaces, was expelled with the large volume of excess adhesive. Where possible, adherend features

were modified to accommodate the adhesive flow control, facilitate subsequent de-moulding, and prevent contamination of critical (hidden) features. For example, the combination of outflow holes on the outer joint surfaces and flow guards on the inside induced the outward resin flow.

7 Results

The results of the FE analyses performed on the combined axial, bending and torsional load cases produced positive margins of safety for all individual components. Table 1 and

Table 2 summarize the stress analysis results and calculated margins. A factor of safety of three was applied. Fig. 11 and Fig. 12 depict typical distributions of the Tsai-Wu failure criterion in a composite adherend and the Von Mises combined stress in an aluminum adherend.

As designed, the lay-up, geometry and material selection satisfied all of the stiffness and strength requirements with positive and healthy margins.

The *A4EI* bondline analysis was performed inclusive of the ultimate axial, torque and combined axial and torque load cases. The combined stresses, as determined using the root sum squares method, predicted a distribution of shear stress as shown in Fig. 13. For clarity, a schematic and a stepped-lap joint cross-section micrograph are also presented.

Based on the bonded joint analysis, both the adherends and the adhesive in the NGLC bonded joint show high positive margins of safety (greater than 6).

The results of the two rail network bonding exercises were very encouraging with uneventful de-moulding of the bonded articles. A visual inspection of the bondlines revealed uniform bondline thickness with generous adhesive squeeze-out and no gaps as shown in Fig. 14.

The stepped-lap bonding exercises were equally successful though more difficult to execute due to their inherent complexity and the article sizes. De-moulding of the outer segment articles was particularly challenging, with difficult access to the flow guards protecting the rail network. A total of ten stepped-lap bonding operations were performed, yielding four assemblies and two reduced-size

stepped lap articles for subsequent destructive testing.

Visual inspection of sectioned bondlines under microscope revealed good bondline quality with respect to thickness and void content. Fig. 15 shows a typical bondline with the precise placement of the 0° plies in the composite adherend visible at the bondline. This correct placement of the 0° plies at each of the steps in all of the interfaces examined represents a notable success as it provides visual confirmation of the developed ply placement methodology. As previously mentioned, this was challenging to develop since the operation was performed in a “blind” sense, with no in-process validation of the position of the 0° plies, relying entirely upon analytical methods and tow data, and based on preliminary tests focused on process-induced thickness consolidation.

Verification of bondline strength was accomplished via destructive tensile testing of bonded stepped-lap coupons, extracted as longitudinal segments from the aforementioned reduced-size articles bonded for this purpose using the manufacturing and bonding methods described above. Appropriate experimental and analytical tools were utilized to compensate for the additional peel loading condition experienced by the coupons (but not present in the full cylindrical joints). Preliminary results of these on-going coupon tests indicate a good agreement with the bondline analyses.

8 Conclusions

The NGLC test bed successfully demonstrated the design, development, manufacture and integration of a large manipulator system with a reduced launch package while still maintaining the desired reach capability of existing systems. The adherend and joint designs were driven by performance and programmatic metrics, and were facilitated by using existing and customized design tools. The bonded joints and the execution of the bonding operations were successful as revealed by bondline micrography and destructive testing. The final integration of the bonded composite assemblies into the NGLC test bed are shown in Fig. 16 and Fig. 17.

Developments in structural bonding of large adherends, carbon composite manufacturing, telescopic actuation and locking, as well as many

other technologies, were instrumental to the success of the design.

It is well understood that in a flight design, several material and geometric changes would be required. These changes may include the introduction of an ultra-high modulus carbon fibre with a cyanate ester matrix for increased stiffness, dimensional and thermal stability and general robustness in the space environment. Replacement of the aluminum sections with titanium for galvanic and CTE matching is also recommended, in addition to creating a double-sided stepped-lap joint for improved load handling and durability. Further optimization could be achieved by utilizing high-strength structural film adhesives, allowing for overall mass reduction while maintaining, or improving, load-carrying capabilities.

9 Acknowledgements

The authors wish to extend their gratitude to the Canadian Space Agency (CSA) for their support of the Next Generation Canadarm program, of which NGLC was one of five developed test beds.

In addition, the authors wish to acknowledge CST Composites (New South Wales, Australia) for their dedicated support in providing important filament winding tow data and subsequent fabrication of NGLC composite sections.

10 References

- [1] S. Rossi. "Next generation large Canadarm (NGLC) test bed requirements specification". MDA-NGC-SG.10751, 2011.
- [2] L.J. Hart-Smith. "Adhesively bonded joints for fibrous composite structures". *International Symposium on Joining and Repair of Fibre-Reinforced Plastics, London, United Kingdom, September 1986*.
- [3] L.J. Hart-Smith. "Design methodology for bonded-bolted composite joints vol. 1 analysis, derivations and illustrative solutions". AFWAL-TR-81-3154 Vol. 1, 1982.
- [4] H, Kim and K. Kedward. "Stress analysis of in-plane, shear-loaded, adhesively bonded composite joints and assemblies". DOT/FAA/AR-01/7, 2001.
- [5] D. Djokic, P. P. Krimbalis, G. Hay, R. Cole, J. Rogers and S. Brunet. "Structural bonding of the next generation large Canadarm (NGLC) ground test

bed". *SAMPE Fall Technical Conference Proceedings, Charleston, SC, October 22-25, 2012*.

- [6] G. Hay. "NGLC Mechanical Design Report". MDA-NGC-R.11078, 2011.
- [7] G. Hay, P. P. Krimbalis. "NGLC Telescopic Boom Adhesive Bonding". NGC.139219, 2010.
- [8] P.P. Krimbalis. "NGLC Composite Boom Material Selection and Stiffness Analysis". NGC.138822, 2010.
- [9] P.P. Krimbalis. "NGLC Step Lap Joint Analysis". NGC.145248, 2011.

FIGURES

Fig. 1. NGLC test bed assembly schematic

Fig. 4. Machined stepped-lap joint

Fig. 2. Legacy boom end-fitting showing protruding Hi-Lok® fastener tails

Fig. 3. Legacy boom end fitting cross-section

Fig. 5. Schematic of the rail bonding configuration

Fig. 6. Bonded rail configuration

Fig. 9. Application of paste adhesive

Fig. 7. Stepped-lap bonding configuration

Fig. 8. Stepped-lap joint bonding

Fig. 10. Schematic of adherend translation process

DESIGN AND VALIDATION OF THE PRIMARY STRUCTURE AND BONDED JOINTS FOR THE NEXT GENERATION LARGE CANADARM GROUND TEST BED

Fig. 11. Typical distribution of the Tsai-Wu failure index

Fig. 12. Typical Von Mises stress distribution

Fig. 13. Adhesive shear stress from combined axial and torsion load case

Fig. 14. Typical bonded rail result

Fig. 15. Stepped-lap joint cross-section

Fig. 16. NGLC ground test bed after integration (booms extended)

Fig. 17. Fully integrated NGLC ground test bed with representative MLI installed (booms retracted)

TABLES

Table 1. Summary of stress analysis results

Parameter	Value	Ply Identifier
σ_{11} [MPa]	-65.14	3
σ_{22} [MPa]	0.91	2
τ_{\max} [MPa]	32.44	3
Tsai-Wu [/]	0.0189	2
Bond Failure [/]	0.0076	17

Table 2. Summary of the calculated margins of safety (MOS)

MOS Index	MOS
σ_{11}	≥ 5
σ_{22}	≥ 5
τ_{\max}	3.29
Tsai-Wu Index	$\ll 1$
Bond Failure Index	$\ll 1$